

Electrochemical behavior of 4-acetylbiphenyl semicarbazone and 4-acetylbiphenyl thiosemicarbazone

Rekha Sangtyani, J. Rawat, P. S. Verma, A. K. Varshney and S. Varshney*

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : saritavarshney@rediffmail.com

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Abstract : Electrochemical kinetic parameters of 4-acetylbiphenyl semicarbazone (4-AcBpSC) and 4-acetylbiphenyl thiosemicarbazone (4-AcBpTSC) in DMF media were measured using cyclic voltammetry on glassy carbon electrode (GCE) at several sweep rates, different concentrations and pH. Both the compounds exhibit a single diffusion controlled irreversible reduction peak. The charge-transfer coefficient (α_n), diffusion coefficient ($D_0^{1/2}$) and rate constant ($k_{f,h}^\circ$) values have been reported.

Keywords : Semicarbazone, thiosemicarbazone, DMF, electrochemical kinetic parameters.

Introduction

A number of studies were reported on voltammetric behavior of semicarbazone¹⁻⁶ and thiosemicarbazone and their derivatives⁷⁻¹⁴. Reddy *et al.*⁵ investigated the electrochemical reduction of 3,4-dimethylacetophenone semicarbazone and *o*-methoxyacetophenone semicarbazone. The single pH dependent reduction wave observed in acid media was ascribed to the $4e^-$ reduction of the protonated azomethine ($>C=N$) group in semicarbazone moiety. Kitaev *et al.*⁸ and Lund^{9,10} reported that the reduction of aromatic thiosemicarbazones should occur through the transfer of 4 electrons but in steps as the cleavage of N-N single bond by reduction with 2 electrons and reduction by two electrons at the imine formed.

In view of conflicting results on the reduction of semicarbazone and thiosemicarbazone, we have taken up a systematic study on the cyclic voltammetry of 4-acetylbiphenyl semicarbazone (4-AcBpSC) and 4-acetylbiphenyl thiosemicarbazone (4-AcBpTSC) in *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF) using phosphate buffer including $HClO_4$. A few electrochemical parameters have been evaluated and a plausible reaction mechanism has been proposed.

Results and discussion

4-AcBpSC and 4-AcBpTSC were synthesized and characterized by IR, ¹H NMR and elemental analysis.

Electrochemical results :

The electrochemical behavior of 4-AcBpSC and 4-AcBpTSC in DMF containing a phosphate buffer and $HClO_4$ were investigated by cyclic voltammetry on a glassy carbon electrode. Voltammetric data obtained are given in Tables 1 and 2 and a few cyclic voltammograms as representatives are shown in Fig. 1. The shape of reduction wave shows clearly the irreversible nature of electrode process. It was confirmed from the linear dependence of the cathodic peak potential E_{pc} with $\ln v$ (Fig. 2)¹⁷. As shown in Fig 1, the cathodic peak potential shifted to more negative direction with the increase of the scan rate indicating to diffusion controlled nature of the electrode process. The magnitude of peak current I_p was found to rise linearly with square root of sweep rate $v^{1/2}$ (Fig 3) focusing diffusion controlled nature of reduction.

The kinetic parameters, charge-transfer coefficient (α_n), diffusion coefficient ($D_0^{1/2}$) and rate constant ($k_{f,h}^\circ$) were calculated for irreversible and diffusion controlled reduction using following eqs.^{13,16-21} (1-3) and reported in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. Effect of sweep rate on voltammetric parameters of 1 mM 4-AcBpSC in DMF solution containing phosphate buffer and 25 mM HClO₄

pH	ν (mV s ⁻¹)	$E_{p,c}$ (mV)	$I_{p,c}$ (μ A)	$E_{p/2}$ (mV)	$E_{1/2}$ (mV)	$I_{p,c}/\nu^{1/2}$	α_n	$D_0^{1/2} \times 10^3$ (cm s ⁻¹)	$k^{\circ}_{f,h}$ (cm s ⁻¹)
5.5	50	-872	1.47	-764	-815	0.2079	0.4418	0.98	6.07×10^{-10}
	100	-876	1.99	-750	-823	0.1999	0.3786	1.02	6.61×10^{-9}
	200	-879	2.87	-741	-825	0.2029	0.3457	1.09	2.81×10^{-8}
	300	-888	3.40	-752	-834	0.1963	0.3508	1.04	2.48×10^{-8}
	400	-898	3.93	-769	-842	0.1965	0.3698	1.02	1.28×10^{-8}
	500	-900	4.38	-773	-840	0.1959	0.3757	1.00	1.13×10^{-8}
7	50	-953	1.18	-806	-902	0.2680	0.3245	0.92	9.37×10^{-9}
	100	-983	2.51	-768	-906	0.251	0.2219	1.68	6.95×10^{-7}
	200	-988	3.02	-728	-912	0.2135	0.1835	1.57	3.51×10^{-6}
	300	-1005	3.66	-768	-923	0.2113	0.2013	1.48	1.88×10^{-6}
	400	-1014	3.86	-772	-922	0.193	0.1971	1.37	2.17×10^{-6}
	500	-1005	4.35	-638	-930	0.1945	0.1300	1.70	3.63×10^{-5}
8.5	50	-1040	1.55	-718	-961	0.2192	0.1482	1.79	5.20×10^{-6}
	100	-1053	2.16	-672	-967	0.216	0.1252	1.92	1.72×10^{-5}
	200	-1071	3.22	-654	-980	0.2277	0.1144	2.12	3.69×10^{-5}
	300	-1102	4.18	-700	-986	0.3413	0.1187	2.20	3.47×10^{-5}
	400	-1089	5.13	-661	-995	0.2565	0.1115	2.42	6.15×10^{-5}
	500	-1104	5.78	-565	-994	0.2585	0.8852	2.73	1.74×10^{-4}

Table 2. Effect of sweep rate on voltammetric parameters of 1 mM 4-AcBpTSC in DMF solution containing phosphate buffer and 25 mM HClO₄

pH	ν (mV s ⁻¹)	$E_{p,c}$ (mV)	$I_{p,c}$ (μ A)	$E_{p/2}$ (mV)	$E_{1/2}$ (mV)	$I_{p,c}/\nu^{1/2}$	α_n	$D_0^{1/2} \times 10^3$ (cm s ⁻¹)	$k^{\circ}_{f,h}$ (cm s ⁻¹)
5.5	50	-859	2.04	-750	-788	0.2884	0.4377	1.37	1.21×10^{-9}
	100	-876	3.61	-731	-793	0.361	0.3290	1.98	6.5×10^{-8}
	200	-894	5.00	-748	-811	0.3535	0.3268	1.95	7.75×10^{-8}
	300	-899	5.96	-762	-824	0.3441	0.3482	1.83	4.09×10^{-8}
	400	-910	6.90	-774	-826	0.345	0.3508	1.83	3.72×10^{-8}
	500	-917	7.86	-775	-835	0.3515	0.3360	1.91	6.54×10^{-8}
7	50	-885	2.23	-778	-813	0.3154	0.4459	1.49	6.39×10^{-10}
	100	-901	4.11	-776	-827	0.411	0.3817	2.09	8.48×10^{-9}
	200	-917	5.23	-801	-831	0.3698	0.4113	1.81	2.96×10^{-9}
	300	-925	6.39	-809	-842	0.3689	0.4113	1.81	3.18×10^{-9}
	400	-929	7.18	-805	-849	0.359	0.3848	1.82	8.75×10^{-9}
	500	-938	8.06	-799	-855	0.3604	0.3432	1.94	3.91×10^{-8}
8.5	50	-927	2.06	-792	-842	0.2913	0.3534	1.54	8.02×10^{-9}
	100	-935	3.71	-774	-849	0.371	0.2963	2.14	1.03×10^{-7}
	200	-941	4.72	-799	-864	0.3337	0.3360	1.81	2.87×10^{-8}
	300	-968	5.66	-809	-871	0.3268	0.3001	1.88	9.36×10^{-8}
	400	-969	6.16	-819	-875	0.308	0.3182	1.72	5.11×10^{-8}
	500	-974	6.84	-824	-878	0.3059	0.3181	1.71	5.33×10^{-8}

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of 1 mM 4-AcBpTSC in DMF solution containing phosphate buffer and 25 mM HClO₄ at pH 5.5.

Fig. 2. Effect of scan rate on cathodic peak potential of 4-AcBpTSC in aqueous DMF solution containing phosphate buffer and 25 mM HClO₄ at pH 5.5.

$$|E_p - E_{p/2}| = \frac{1.857RT}{\alpha_n F} = \left(\frac{47.7}{\alpha_n}\right) mV \quad (1)$$

$$I_p = 3.01 \times 10^5 n(\alpha_n)^{1/2} A C D_0^{1/2} v^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

$$E_p = \frac{RT}{\alpha_n F} \left[0.78 + \ln\left(\frac{D_0^{1/2}}{k_{f,h}^0}\right) + \ln\left(\frac{\alpha_n F v}{RT}\right)^{1/2} \right] \quad (3)$$

Fig. 4 shows the variation of peak potentials (E_{pc}) with electrolyte pH. The cathodic peak potentials have negative shift with increasing pH. An increase in pH value would increase dissociation of protonated species and affect the protonation rate. Consequently, $E_{1/2}$ values of the reduction waves would shift to more negative values²². The observed dependence of $E_{1/2}$ on pH suggests

Fig. 3. Variation of current (I_p) versus $v^{1/2}$ for 1 mM 4-AcBpTSC in aqueous DMF solution containing phosphate buffer and 25 mM HClO₄ at pH 5.5.

Table 3. Effect of sweep rate on voltammetric parameters for different concentration of 4-AcBpSC in DMF solution containing phosphate buffer and 25 mM HClO₄

pH	C (mM)	v (mV s ⁻¹)	E _{p,c} (mV)	I _{p,c} (μA)	E _{p/2} (mV)	E _{1/2} (mV)	I _{p,c} /v ^{1/2}	α _n	D ₀ ^{1/2} × 10 ³ (cm s ⁻¹)	k ^o _{f,h} (cm s ⁻¹)
5.5	1	50	-872	1.47	-764	-815	0.2079	0.4418	0.98	6.07 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
		100	-876	1.99	-750	-823	0.1999	0.3786	1.02	6.61 × 10 ⁻⁹
		200	-879	2.87	-741	-825	0.2029	0.3457	1.09	2.81 × 10 ⁻⁸
		300	-888	3.40	-752	-834	0.1963	0.3508	1.04	2.48 × 10 ⁻⁸
		400	-898	3.93	-769	-842	0.1965	0.3698	1.02	1.28 × 10 ⁻⁸
5.5	2	50	-928	2.77	-804	-850	0.3917	0.3847	1.99	3.42 × 10 ⁻⁹
		100	-936	3.96	-780	-843	0.396	0.3058	2.25	7.72 × 10 ⁻⁸
		200	-952	5.82	-761	-849	0.4115	0.3498	2.59	7.49 × 10 ⁻⁷
		300	-959	7.26	-775	-859	0.4192	0.2593	2.59	6.12 × 10 ⁻⁷
		400	-970	8.42	-788	-860	0.421	0.2621	2.59	5.70 × 10 ⁻⁷
5.5	3	50	-948	2.06	-818	-868	0.2913	0.367	1.51	3.64 × 10 ⁻⁹
		200	-964	4.44	-773	-882	0.3139	0.2498	1.98	5.08 × 10 ⁻⁷
		300	-979	5.50	-781	-889	0.3175	0.2410	2.04	7.62 × 10 ⁻⁷
		400	-986	6.63	-767	-893	0.3315	0.2178	2.23	2.09 × 10 ⁻⁶
		500	-994	7.90	-768	-901	0.3533	0.2111	2.42	3.02 × 10 ⁻⁶

Table 4. Effect of sweep rate on voltammetric parameters for different concentration of 4-AcBpTSC in DMF solution containing phosphate buffer and 25 mM HClO₄

pH	C (mM)	v (mV s ⁻¹)	E _{p,c} (mV)	I _{p,c} (μA)	E _{p/2} (mV)	E _{1/2} (mV)	I _{p,c} /v ^{1/2}	α _n	D ₀ ^{1/2} × 10 ⁻³ (cm s ⁻¹)	k ^o _{f,h} (cm s ⁻¹)
8.5	1	50	-927	2.06	-792	-842	0.2913	0.3534	1.54	8.02 × 10 ⁻⁹
		100	-935	3.71	-774	-849	0.371	0.2963	2.14	1.03 × 10 ⁻⁷
		200	-941	4.72	-799	-864	0.3337	0.3360	1.81	2.87 × 10 ⁻⁸
		300	-968	5.66	-809	-871	0.3268	0.3001	1.88	9.36 × 10 ⁻⁸
		400	-969	6.16	-819	-875	0.308	0.3182	1.72	5.11 × 10 ⁻⁸
8.5	2	50	-974	6.84	-824	-878	0.3059	0.3181	1.71	5.33 × 10 ⁻⁸
		100	-968	2.61	-841	-873	0.3691	0.3757	1.89	2.5 × 10 ⁻⁹
		200	-993	4.07	-854	-887	0.407	0.3432	2.19	9.47 × 10 ⁻⁹
		300	-1007	5.59	-844	-900	0.3952	0.2927	2.30	7.83 × 10 ⁻⁸
		400	-1021	6.53	-864	-906	0.377	0.3039	2.15	5.0 × 10 ⁻⁸
8.5	3	50	-1043	7.39	-848	-909	0.3695	0.2447	2.35	4.83 × 10 ⁻⁷
		100	-1049	8.24	-869	-922	0.3685	0.2651	2.25	2.21 × 10 ⁻⁷
		200	-1031	3.40	-856	-889	0.4808	0.2726	2.90	8.11 × 10 ⁻⁸
		300	-1029	5.02	-835	-900	0.502	0.2459	3.19	3.56 × 10 ⁻⁷
		400	-1112	8.36	-874	-925	0.4827	0.2005	3.39	1.92 × 10 ⁻⁶
8.5	3	400	-1085	9.24	-872	-934	0.462	0.2240	3.07	9.70 × 10 ⁻⁷
		500	-1121	10.24	-893	-936	0.4579	0.2092	3.15	1.49 × 10 ⁻⁶

fast proton transfer precede the main electrode process. Effect of concentration of electroactive species on cathodic peak potential and peak current has been studied.

The voltammetric data shows that peak potential shifts in negative direction and peak current increases with increasing the concentration of electroactive species indi-

Fig. 4. Effect of scan rate on cathodic peak potential for 1 mM 4-AcBpSC in aqueous DMF solution containing phosphate buffer and 25 mM HClO₄ at pH 5.5.

Table 5. Effect of sweep rate on voltammetric parameters of 1 mM 4-AcBpTSC in DMF solution containing phosphate buffer (pH 8.5) at different concentration of HClO₄

HClO ₄ conc. (mM)	v (mV s ⁻¹)	E _{p,c} (mV)	I _{p,c} (μA)	E _{p/2} (mV)	E _{1/2} (mV)	I _{p,c} /v ^{1/2}	α _n	D ₀ ^{1/2} × 10 ³ (cm s ⁻¹)	k ^o _{f,h} (cm s ⁻¹)
5	50	-1400	2.36	-1287	-1332	0.3337	0.4222	1.62	3.21 × 10 ⁻¹³
	100	-1415	3.77	-1289	-1332	0.377	0.3786	1.93	4.42 × 10 ⁻¹²
	200	-1442	5.08	-1300	-1354	0.3592	0.3360	1.95	4.39 × 10 ⁻¹¹
	300	-1450	6.02	-1306	-1370	0.3476	0.3313	1.90	6.1 × 10 ⁻¹¹
	400	-1465	7.08	-1320	-1382	0.354	0.3290	1.94	6.73 × 10 ⁻¹¹
	500	-1479	8.08	-1331	-1391	0.3613	0.3224	2.00	9.43 × 10 ⁻¹¹
25	50	-927	2.06	-792	-842	0.2913	0.3534	1.54	8.02 × 10 ⁻⁹
	100	-935	3.71	-774	-849	0.371	0.2963	2.14	1.03 × 10 ⁻⁷
	200	-941	4.72	-799	-864	0.3337	0.3360	1.81	2.87 × 10 ⁻⁸
	300	-968	5.66	-809	-871	0.3268	0.3001	1.88	9.36 × 10 ⁻⁸
	400	-969	6.16	-819	-875	0.308	0.3182	1.72	5.11 × 10 ⁻⁸
	500	-974	6.84	-824	-878	0.3059	0.3181	1.71	5.33 × 10 ⁻⁸

Table 6. Effect of sweep rate on voltammetric parameters of 1 mM 4-AcBpTSC in DMF solution containing phosphate buffer (pH 7) at different concentration of HClO₄

HClO ₄ conc. (mM)	v (mV s ⁻¹)	E _{p,c} (mV)	I _{p,c} (μA)	E _{p/2} (mV)	E _{1/2} (mV)	I _{p,c} /v ^{1/2}	α _n	D ₀ ^{1/2} × 10 ³ (cm s ⁻¹)	k ^o _{f,h} (cm s ⁻¹)
5	50	-1382	2.27	-1232	-1299	0.3210	0.3181	1.79	1.13 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
	100	-1401	3.49	-1219	-1314	0.349	0.2621	2.14	2.9 × 10 ⁻⁹
	200	-1426	4.97	-1202	-1306	0.3514	0.2130	2.40	4.90 × 10 ⁻⁸
	300	-1431	6.08	-1218	-1347	0.3510	0.2240	2.33	3.12 × 10 ⁻⁸
	400	-1441	7.07	-1234	-1356	0.3535	0.2305	2.32	2.31 × 10 ⁻⁸
	500	-1452	7.96	-1250	-1365	0.3560	0.2362	2.30	1.70 × 10 ⁻⁸

									Table-6 (contd.)
25	50	-885	2.23	-778	-813	0.3154	0.4459	1.49	6.39×10^{-10}
	100	-901	4.11	-776	-827	0.411	0.3817	2.09	8.48×10^{-9}
	200	-917	5.23	-801	-831	0.3698	0.4113	1.81	2.96×10^{-9}
	300	-925	6.39	-809	-842	0.3689	0.4113	1.81	3.18×10^{-9}
	400	-929	7.18	-805	-849	0.359	0.3848	1.82	8.75×10^{-9}
	500	-938	8.06	-799	-855	0.3604	0.3432	1.94	3.91×10^{-8}

Table 7. Effect of sweep rate on voltammetric parameters of 1 mM 4-AcBpTSC in DMF solution containing phosphate buffer (pH 5.5) at different concentration of HClO₄

HClO ₄ conc. (mM)	v (mV s ⁻¹)	E _{p,c} (mV)	I _{p,c} (μA)	E _{p/2} (mV)	E _{1/2} (mV)	I _{p,c} /v ^{1/2}	α _n	D ₀ ^{1/2} × 10 ⁻³ (cm s ⁻¹)	k ^o _{f,h} (cm s ⁻¹)
5	50	-979	2.06	-860	-896	0.2913	0.4009	1.45	6.4×10^{-10}
	100	-977	3.39	-842	-904	0.339	0.3534	1.79	6.63×10^{-9}
	200	-1022	4.64	-859	-922	0.3281	0.2927	1.91	5.47×10^{-8}
	300	-1028	5.38	-868	-929	0.3106	0.2982	1.79	4.76×10^{-8}
	400	-1032	6.12	-874	-938	0.306	0.3020	1.75	4.44×10^{-8}
25	50	-859	2.04	-750	-788	0.2884	0.4377	1.37	1.21×10^{-9}
	100	-876	3.61	-731	-793	0.361	0.3290	1.98	6.5×10^{-8}
	200	-894	5.00	-748	-811	0.3535	0.3268	1.95	7.75×10^{-8}
	300	-899	5.96	-762	-824	0.3441	0.3482	1.83	4.09×10^{-8}
	400	-910	6.90	-774	-826	0.345	0.3508	1.83	3.72×10^{-8}
500	-917	7.86	-775	-835	0.3515	0.3360	1.91	6.54×10^{-8}	

cating that the reduction products are adsorbed over the electrode surface²³⁻²⁵. The cathodic peak current value (I_p) however, is not regular for 4-AcBpSC at pH 5.5 for 3 mM concentration. This discrepancy may be due to the chemical properties of depolarizer, its steric effect and double layer formation at the electrode surface, which is affected by adsorption of neutral molecule, which hinders the electrode reaction. Increasing concentration of HClO₄ has an effect on peak potential since the peak potential shifts in positive direction because of the decrease in the pH of experimental solution as the concentration of HClO₄ has increased which shows the involvement of proton in reduction process supporting the reduction mechanism. The magnitude of transfer coefficient (< 1) and rate constant ($\leq 2 \times 10^{-5}$) also support the irreversible nature of electrode process.

The results obtained in the present studies show that the 4-AcBpSC and 4-AcBpTSC presently investigated undergo easily reduction. The azomethine group (>C=N) present in the compound is reduced to the corresponding amino group in a four electron process. This kind of

reduction behavior was also observed in some aromatic semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones⁴⁻⁷. On the basis of the above result of the present investigation as well as on the basis of the literature data, the reduction mechanism shown in Scheme 1 may be proposed for the compound^{1,6-10,19,21,26}

Experimental

Synthesis of 4-AcBpSC and 4-AcBpTSC :

4-AcBpSC and 4-AcBpTSC are prepared by the condensation of 4-acetylbiphenyl with semicarbazide hydrochloride (in presence of sodium acetate) or thiosemicarbazide (in presence of few drops of glacial acetic acid) in 1 : 1 molar ratio in methanol. They are recrystallised and dried *in vacuo*. 4-AcBpSC [yield : 74%, colour : cream, m.p. 238 °C; Calcd. C, 71.13; H, 5.97; N, 16.59. Found : C, 71.87; H, 5.45; N, 15.9%; IR (KBr pellet, cm⁻¹) : 3459 and 3381 (NH₂), 3164 (NH), 1664 (C=N), 1710 (C=O); ¹H NMR (mixture of CDCl₃ and DMSO-d₆, δ) : 6.54 (NH₂), 9.39 (NH), 2.20 (CH₃), 7.18-7.90 (ArH)]. 4-AcBpTSC [yield : 68%, colour : cream, m.p.

where X=O or S

Scheme 1. Proposed reduction mechanism for semicarbazone/thiosemicarbazone.

221 °C; Calcd. C, 66.91; H, 5.58; N, 15.61; S, 11.90. Found : C, 67.19; H, 5.85; N, 15.12; S, 11.15%; IR (KBr pellet, cm⁻¹) : 3473 and 3380 (NH₂), 3140 (NH), 1596 (C=N)^{27,28}, 1098 (C=S); ¹H NMR (mixture of CDCl₃ and DMSO-*d*₆, δ) : 8.26 (NH₂), 10.03 (NH), 2.3 (CH₃), 7.42-7.91 (ArH).

Physical measurement :

Melting points were recorded on a Mel-temp apparatus. Carbon and hydrogen analysis was carried out on Column analyzer, which was standardized first with A.R. benzoic acid and Kjeldahl's method was used to estimate nitrogen. Sulphur was estimated as barium sulphate by Messenger's method. IR spectra were recorded on a FTIR spectrometer (Model 8400S, Shimadzu) in the 4000-400 cm⁻¹ range using KBr discs. NMR spectra were recorded in a mixture of CDCl₃ and DMSO-*d*₆ (1 : 1 v/v) with a 300.4 MHz FT NMR spectrometer (Model Jeol AL 300). The pH measurements were carried out with an Elico digital pH meter.

Electrochemical measurements :

Electrochemical measurements were made with a fully computer controlled Basic Electrochemistry System (Model

ECDA 001) equipped with a three electrode system consisting of a glassy carbon working electrode, a platinum wire as auxiliary and Ag|AgCl reference electrode. The stock solutions of the compounds (1 × 10⁻² M) were prepared in dimethylformamide. Phosphate buffer and 0.5 M HClO₄ were prepared in doubly distilled water. The working solutions were prepared by taking 1 ml of stock solution of the compound, DMF (the minimum volume necessary to keep the compound in the solution), 0.5 ml of 0.5 M HClO₄. Final solution was made up to 10 ml by adding phosphate buffer. Cyclic voltammograms of the compounds were recorded in the potential range (-1400 to +1400 mV) at different scan rates 50, 100, 200, 300, 400 and 500 mV/s and three different pH (5.5, 7 and 8.5). All solutions were purged with nitrogen for 15 min before measurements and the working electrode was polished before each experiment with an alumina solution.

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